

Dipole Moments of Polyphenylene Polyethers and Polyphenylene Polysulphides

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The dipole moments of some polyphenylene polyethers and polyphenylene polysulphides have been determined and the values compared with the calculated ones assuming free rotation of all the dipoles. The lack of agreement between the two values for $C_6H_4OC_6H_4OC_6H_4OC_6H_4OC_6H_4$, $C_6H_4SC_6H_4SC_6H_4SC_6H_4$ and $C_6H_4SC_6H_4SC_6H_4SC_6H_4SC_6H_4$ is attributed to inhibition of free rotation as the length of the molecules increases.

THE nonavailability of dipole moment data on polyphenylene polyethers and polyphenylene polysulphides and the interest associated with the influence of chain-length on dipole moments prompted us to undertake this study. Since the molecules of each series have increasing length, any information on rotation or restricted rotation of parts of the molecule under the conditions of study (solution state) is also of interest.

Experimental

The compounds were prepared according to the reported methods. The literature data¹⁻⁴ of physical constants are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MELTING/BOILING POINTS OF POLYPHENYLENE POLYETHERS AND POLYSULPHIDES

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p./B.p. °C	Lit. M.p./B.p. °C
1.	1,4-Diphenoxybenzene	76-7	75.5-76.5 ^a
2.	Bis(<i>p</i> -phenoxyphenyl) ether	108-09	110 ^a
3.	Bis(<i>p</i> -phenoxyphenyl) ether of <i>p</i> -hydroquinone	149-50	151 ^b
4.	1,4-Diphenylthiobenzene	79-80	81.5 ^c
5.	Bis(<i>p</i> -phenylthiophenyl) sulphide	99-100	99-100 ^d
6.	1,4-Di(<i>p</i> -phenylthio)-phenylthiobenzene	128-29	128-29 ^d
7.	<i>m</i> -Diphenoxybenzene	60-61	61.5 ^a
8.	<i>m</i> -Diphenylthiobenzene	227-28/ 16 mm	227-28/ 16 mm ^d

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 3. ^dRef. 4.

All measurements were made in benzene solution at $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The apparatus for measuring dielectric constants is described in an earlier paper⁵. Density was measured with a 10 ml pycnometer. Explanation of symbols used and the method of calculating dipole moments are given in a previous communication⁶. R_D was estimated from bond refractions⁷. A value of 0.8 ml was added for each Ar-S bond to account for the exaltation in molar refraction due to

this bond. This value was computed from the difference between the calculated and observed values of *m*-diphenylthiobenzene and that of many other aryl sulphides⁶. Considering the high value of molar refraction, 5% of the value was added to it as contribution of the atom polarisation. The polarisation data and the dipole moments are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—POLARISATION DATA AND DIPOLE MOMENTS AT 30°

n	ϵ	β	∞P_s ml	R_D ml	$\mu(D)$	
					Found	Calcd.
X=O						
1	0.4530	0.2549	122.6	78.7	1.41	1.45
2	0.4765	0.2779	159.9	105.0	1.57	1.59
3	0.5844	0.1500	201.2	131.2	1.78	1.66
X=S						
1	0.7548	0.2926	166.6	94.3	1.83	1.75
2	0.8001	0.3154	232.5	128.2	2.20	1.79
3	0.9410	0.1928	290.8	162.1	2.45	1.84

X=O 0.5672 0.2466 131.4 78.7 1.56 1.56
X=S 0.8569 0.2827 180.5 95.4 1.96 2.00

Results and Discussion

The calculation of the dipole moment of a molecule containing two or more dipoles, which may change their directions relative to one another by rotation around bonds between atoms, requires averaging over all possible positions around the bonds. A method of effecting this average was given as a general equation by Eyring⁸ and as a

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number of special equations for individual molecules by Smyth and Walls⁹. The method was illustrated by Smyth¹⁰ by calculating the dipole moment of β , β' -dichlorodiethyl ether.

The application of Eyring's equation to the calculation of the dipole moment of a compound like **1** for complete free rotation of bonds may be made from the moment of diphenyl ether (1.17 D)¹¹ and

the COC angle (123°)¹² as shown in Fig. 1. The

Fig. 1

angles made by the directed lines connecting the pair O₁A and O₂B can be obtained by resolving the O₁A moment along O₁O₂ and then along O₂B. A similar procedure can be adopted for other pairs :

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^2 &= 4 \times 1.17^2 + 2 \times 3 \times 1.17^2 \cos 61.5^\circ \cos 118.5^\circ \\ &\quad + 2 \times 2 \times 1.17^2 \cos 61.5^\circ \cos 57^\circ \cos 118.5^\circ \\ &\quad + 2 \times 1.17^2 \cos 61.5^\circ \cos 57^\circ \cos 57^\circ \cos 118.5^\circ \\ &= 2.74 \\ \mu &= 1.66 \text{ D} \end{aligned}$$

In the same way the dipole moment of the sulphur compound **2** can also be calculated.

The CSC angle¹³ is 109.5° and the dipole moment

of diphenyl sulphide¹¹ is 1.51 D. Hence the mean square moment may be written as :

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^2 &= 3 \times 1.52^2 + 2 \times 2 \times 1.52^2 \cos 54^\circ 45' \\ &\quad \cos 125^\circ 15' + 2 \times 1.52^2 \cos 54^\circ 45' \\ &\quad \cos 70^\circ 30' \cos 125^\circ 15' \\ &= 3.21 \\ \mu &= 1.79 \text{ D} \end{aligned}$$

The dipole moment of *m*-diphenoxybenzene can be calculated using Fuchs' equation¹⁴,

$$\mu^2 = \mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + 2\mu_1\mu_2 \cos \theta \cos \alpha \cos \beta$$

which in the present case, reduces to

$$\mu^2 = 2 \times 1.17^2 + 2 \times 1.17^2 \cos 120^\circ \cos 61.5^\circ$$

The calculated as well as the observed moments of all the polyphenylene polyethers and their sulphur analogues are given in Table 2.

There is a good agreement between the calculated and observed values for compounds having three benzene rings ($n=1$) in a molecule. In the case of oxygen compounds the agreement is good for the four-ring one ($n=2$) also. For other compounds the observed values are higher than the calculated values. This seems to indicate that as the length of the molecule increases, with consequent increase in molecular weight, the free rotation which is assumed in the calculation is hindered.

It may be seen that the sulphur compounds have higher dipole moments than their oxygen analogues. This is generally the case, but not always so, as may be seen from the values given in Table 3. Hunter and Partington¹⁷ explained the differences between the moments of the corresponding sulphur and oxygen compounds largely in terms of the considerable difference in polarisability of oxygen and sulphur. But when sulphur conjugates with an electron-attracting group like NO₂ or COCH₃, the oxygen compound has a higher dipole moment than its sulphur analogue (sl. nos. 8 and 9, Table 1). However, when the conjugation is with an electron-releasing group like NH₂ or CH₃O, sulphur utilises the vacant *d*-orbitals in its valence shell and the sulphur compound has a significantly higher dipole moment than its oxygen analogue (sl. nos. 5-7). Both the 2,6-dimethyl derivatives (sl. no. 11) of anisole and thioanisole have the same dipole moment.

TABLE 3—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF CORRESPONDING SULPHUR AND OXYGEN COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no.	Oxygen compd.	μ D	Sulphur compd.	μ D
1.	CH ₃ OCH ₃	1.30 ^a	CH ₃ SCH ₃	1.41 ^a
2.	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	1.25	C ₆ H ₅ SCH ₃	1.31
3.	C ₆ H ₅ OC ₆ H ₅	1.17 ^b	C ₆ H ₅ SC ₆ H ₅	1.51 ^b
4.	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	1.21 ^a	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .SCH ₃	1.52
5.	4-CH ₃ .O.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	1.71	4-CH ₃ .O.C ₆ H ₄ .SCH ₃	1.98
6.	4-H ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	1.82 ^c	4-H ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .SCH ₃	2.54
7.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	1.76	4-(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .SCH ₃	2.82
8.	4-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	4.85	4-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .SCH ₃	4.43
9.	4-CH ₃ CO.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	3.56 ^a	4-CH ₃ CO.C ₆ H ₄ .SCH ₃	3.13
10.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OCH ₃	2.26 ^a	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .SCH ₃	1.83 ^a
11.	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .OCH ₃	1.24 ^a	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .SCH ₃	1.24

*Unless stated otherwise, the values are from Ref. 6. ^aRef. 15. ^bRef. 11. ^cRef. 16.

It is thus clear that the differences observed between the dipole moments of the corresponding oxygen and sulphur compounds arise not only from the difference in polarisabilities of oxygen and sulphur, but also from the polar, steric and other unrecognised effects operating in the molecules. The problem, therefore, needs to be studied in greater depth with data on more compounds to arrive at a satisfactory explanation.

References

1. F. ULLMANN and P. SPONAGEL, *Annalen*, 1906, **350**, 83.
2. H. STAUDINGER and F. STAIGER, *Annalen*, 1935, **517**, 67.
3. E. BOURGEOIS and A. FOUASSIN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1911, **9**, 938.
4. V. BALIAH and T. GOVINDARAJAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 903.
5. V. BALIAH and K. GANAPATHY, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 1784.
6. V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 455.
7. A. I. VOGEL, W. T. CRESSWELL, G. H. JEFFREY and J. LEICHERSTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 514.
8. H. EYRING, *Phys. Rev.*, 1932, **39**, 746.
9. C. P. SMYTH and W. S. WALLS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2261.
10. C. P. SMYTH, "Dielectric Behaviour and Structure", McGraw Hill, New York, 1955, pp. 234-235.
11. G. C. HAMPSON, R. H. FARMER and L. E. SUTTON, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1933, **143**, 147.
12. J. TOUSSAINT, *Bull. Soc. R. Sci. Liege*, 1946, **15**, 86 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1948, **42**, 7128).
13. J. TOUSSAINT, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1945, **54**, 319.
14. O. FUCHS, *Z. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 1931, **14**, 339.
15. A. L. McCLELLAN, "Tables of Experimental Dipole Moments", Freeman and Company, San Francisco, 1963.
16. J. W. WILLIAMS and J. M. FOLGENBERG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1356.
17. E. C. HUNTER and J. R. PARTINGTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2812, 2819.